

6G-SANDBOX

Supporting Architectural and technological
Network evolutions through an intelligent, secured
and twinning enabled Open eXperimentation
facility

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Networks - Intermediate report

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ABSTRACT

This deliverable includes information about the first cycle of development and integration activities performed across all tasks of Work Package 4 “Integration and management of 6G trial networks” in the project 6G-SANDBOX. A 6G trial network, the main concept in the project, is a fully manageable and configurable network offered as a testbed to an experimenter. Actual components/technologies in the trial networks (core network, RAN, devices, etc.) are provided by the four platforms in the project (Athens, Berlin, Malaga, and Oulu), and they are mainly implemented in Work Package 3 “Open and reusable 6G library for trial networks”. Work Package 4 takes results from WP3 as input to enhance the four platforms and to create the necessary coordination and orchestration process to manage the trial networks. This work package includes three main activities:

- a) building a 6G-SANDBOX framework for deployment, configuration, sharing, coordination and orchestration of the trial network components with information from the library.
- b) constructions of digital twins of some resources/components to be part of the trial networks replacing the actual resources.
- c) expanding the technologies in the existing four platforms with additional components following a well-defined integration process.

The four existing platforms in 6G-SANDBOX are mature infrastructure created and used in previous projects, including 5G PPP and national projects. They are now expanded in 6G-SANDBOX with trial network support and with new components, including digital twins. The objective of this deliverable is to report only on the new features and the activities to add these new features into the project. A full description with all the capabilities per platform is offered in separate documents to be distributed as part of the documentation of experimenters available at <https://www.6g-sandbox.eu>.

KEYWORDS

Trial Network, 6G library, Digital Twins, Integration

1 INTRODUCTION

1.1 DOCUMENT STRUCTURE

This document is organized into three parts. In order to make a self-contained document, the deliverable starts with a summary of 6G-SANDBOX ecosystem and potential users in section 2. A reference to the main supporting tools is also included in this section.

Then, part 2 in sections 3 and 4 are devoted to the 6G-SANDBOX experimentation framework. Section 3 details the status of the trial network manager, which deals with the most high-level aspects of the creation and management of trial networks. Section 4 describes the deployment aspects and use of the virtualized infrastructure to support the trial networks.

In the third part, section 5 reports the integration activities done per platform and includes activities in digital twins as part of the integration in the Malaga platform.

1.2 TARGET AUDIENCE

This document is intended to be useful for the whole SNS JU community and 6G-SANDBOX ecosystem described in Section 2. However, the document is strongly recommended for testbed developers interested in creating a new 6G-SANDBOX platform reusing the framework developed in the project. Such replication is encouraged as part of SNS JU objectives, and it is an objective in 6G-SANDBOX project. The support to replication can be done with the project's open calls or with some other ad-hoc agreement. All of the software tools described in sections 2 and 3 are offered as open source to any interested party.

2 6G-SANDBOX ECOSYSTEM

2.1 6G-SANDBOX ARCHITECTURE AND KEY CONCEPTS

The 6G-SANDBOX Reference Architecture as described in D2.1 [1], follows a structure of 3 layers, wherein each layer abstracts and encapsulates specific functionalities. This design allows for the reduction of perceived complexity by providing a simplified interface to end-users. They can engage with the system without requiring an in-depth understanding of its internal operations. At the same time, this approach divides the inherent complexity into more manageable components, promoting a structured and easily understandable system.

Figure 1. 6G-SANDBOX Architecture.

From bottom to top, the Physical Infrastructure Layer encompasses the tangible elements constituting the 5G/6G network, computational resources, measurement equipment, end-user devices, and any additional devices essential for specific experiments within the testbed. This layer is opted to be expanded by incorporating external resources from other Testbed Domains, experimenter premises, or the public cloud through VPN connectivity. The Resource Management Layer, situated above the Physical Infrastructure layer, employs Infrastructure Managers (OpenNebula, OpenStack, PROXMOX, etc.) to centrally manage the diverse capabilities within the testbeds. Finally, the Experimentation Lifecycle Layer serves as an interface connecting Experimenters (users of a Trial Network) with the underlying Resource Management layer. Its primary function is to oversee the lifecycle of various Trial Networks, encapsulating the testbed resources made accessible to experimenters.

Within the architecture, the TNLCM serves as the core component responsible for orchestrating the creation and management of Trial Networks. Simultaneously, the 6G Library, hosted on the GitHub repository, provides a comprehensive set of software components and accompanying documentation. This initiative aims to establish an open reference software library, facilitating the seamless instantiation of Trial Networks.

Furthermore, the overall architecture aligns with the 3rd Generation Partnership Project (3GPP) approach to Open APIs implementation. This decision is rooted in the necessity for Trial Networks to expose APIs to 6G-SANDBOX users. In accordance with this decision, the chosen API Framework for API exposure is CAPIF, ensuring a standardized and effective interface for interactions with the created Trial Networks.

2.2 EXPERIMENTER PROFILES AND ACCESS LEVEL

Depending on the experimenter, different profiles and access levels have been defined. Table 1 includes a compilation of defined user profiles, indicating for each one the resources available or needed, the level of permissions and some examples of these profiles.

User Profile	Summary	Resources exposed from 6G-SANDBOX	Resources from the user	Access level to 6G-SANDBOX resources	Examples
Vertical App developer	Non-OTT developer of UE and Network side. App software interested in experimentation	Every component exposed with CAPIF in his/her TN	Additional SW/HW linked to the TN	Only access exposed to TN users, basic customization	Typical app developers in Stream D
TN operator	Owner of a long-term TN for internal or third-party experimentation	All the resources to run and customize one or several TN	Additional resources from the TN operator and from third parties as sub-tenants	Advance customization of TNs by software and/or with manual configuration	Stream D Project. Leader of cluster of experimenters (ITRI, Slices). Company in testing as service
Technology provider	Researcher or Company creating new HW/SW as part of the 6G network	TN to plug in the new component. Only support to add the resource to the 6G-Library	The new HW/SW transferred to a platform or in premises	All the access and support granted by the platform to make the integration and testing	Stream A, B project. O-RAN developer. NWDAF developer. mmWave provider. XR device maker. ...
6G-SANDBOX Platform operator	Testbed owner interested in adopting 6G-SANDBOX framework	All the software developed to support the TNs	Usually, some starting 5G/6G testbed to be enhanced	Local copy for full access	5GPPP platforms in ICT-17. Stream C platforms in SNS

Table 1. Experimenter profiles.

2.3 MAIN SUPPORTING TOOLS

Prior to showing the updates in the experimentation framework and the upgrades of the platforms, it is necessary to introduce, as a reference, the main supporting tools that are key parts of this evolution. These tools can be differentiated into deployment tools, orchestration, and testing & measurement. If more information about these tools is needed, deliverables D3.1 and D5.1 can be referenced.

Deployment tools:

These are the necessary tools for the development of components in a Trial Network.

- **Terraform:** This tool facilitates the creation of virtual infrastructure across private cloud providers, enabling the setup of virtual networks, machines, containers, Kubernetes clusters, and more. Terraform streamlines the infrastructure provisioning process.
- **Ansible:** Employed for comprehensive component configuration, equipment setup, and integrations, Ansible enables fine-grained actions on Trial Network components. Its idempotent nature ensures reliability in configurations.
- **Jenkins:** This tool serves as the orchestrator for deploying components, executing deployment processes efficiently. Jenkins streamlines and automates deployment workflows.
- **Bash:** Enabling scripting for standalone operations, Bash provides flexibility and customization in executing various operational tasks.

Orchestration:

OpenNebula is the proposed solution to provide the private cloud infrastructure that will be used in the project. It relies on libvirt, recommending the usage of the KVM hypervisor, providing resource control (authorization/authentication/accounting) via ACLs and POSIX rules with several authentication methods and frontend high availability. OpenNebula provides an XML-RPC interface that can be accessed with different interfaces, for instance:

- OpenNebula command line interface (CLI)
- The graphical web interfaces, Sunstone and FireEdge.
- Terraform (executes instructions over the OpenNebula endpoint)

The networking model for OpenNebula would require three different connections (can be overlapped) as shown in Figure 2, that can be used to emulate the project network necessities.

Figure 2. Networking model of OpenNebula.

Once the OpenNebula infrastructure is running, it provides the creation and access to the following resources:

- **Virtual Networks:** logical partition of networks used to interconnect VMs.
- **Virtual disk images (images):** physical storage that will be treated as a VM disk.
- **Datastores:** volumes to store the necessary data for the VM to run.

- Image datastore: the globally used images.
- System datastore: stores each VM specific image.
- Files: Stores specific files.
- Templates are a way to create VMs and Virtual networks with a similar configuration. A template Instance will generate a VM, thus VM or instance will be used indistinctly for the same concept.

All of the previous resources can be grouped with the usage of:

- Clusters: a logical partition of Nodes, Virtual Networks and datastores.
- Virtual Datacenter (VDC): a logical partition of the previously mentioned resources with access control.

Testing & measurement

These are the tools (software in Table 2 and hardware in Table 3) that Keysight is providing to the platforms.

Software Tool	Definition
Hawkeye	Hawkeye is an active network performance monitoring platform which can be used for QoS monitoring, application and web monitoring, Wi-Fi monitoring, cloud monitoring, etc.
BreakingPointVE	BreakingPoint is a security testing tool for performing penetration testing on network infrastructure.
IxNetwork	IxNetwork is a virtualized network performance testing solution that emulates a wide range of networking protocols and traffic types.
IXLoad	IXLoad is a virtualized multiplay services testing solution that delivers comprehensive functional and performance testing to validate user quality of experience (QoE) in physical and virtual networks.
CloudPeak:	CloudPeak allows the user to validate and benchmark VMware vCenter and OpenStack-based private clouds and can run evaluations on a testbed for a single compute node or large environments with many racks.
Cyperf:	CyPerf supports the creation of digital twin of users, applications, and attacks to replicate and test QoE in real-world network environments.
Threat Simulator	Threat Simulator is a breach and attack simulation platform that provides enterprise security teams with insights into the effectiveness of their security posture and actionable intelligence to improve it.
LoadCore	LoadCore test solution addresses the testing and validation of 5G elements in the core network.
EXata	EXata is a platform for digital twins. It is a discrete event simulation platform that allows modelling and performance evaluation of local area networks (LAN), wide area networks (WAN), wireless networks and communication protocols.
PathWave System Design	PathWave System Design is a software platform that enables RF system architects, designers, and verification teams to create and simulate complex RF systems with high accuracy and speed.

RIC Test	RIC Test emulates O-RAN network nodes and traffic profiles on different RAN Intelligent Controller's (RIC's) interfaces, allowing testing of the Near Real-Time RIC (and of xApps it hosts) and of the Non-Real-Time RIC (and of rApps it hosts).
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Table 2. Keysight Software tools.

Hardware Tool	Definition
Wavejudge	Wavejudge Wireless Analyzer Solutions are a set of over-the-air monitor toolsets that offer users real-time visibility of the interactions between the physical and protocol layers in wireless transmissions.
UeSIM, DuSIM, CuSIM	UeSIM (SW), DuSIM, CuSIM enable infrastructure vendors, chipset providers and mobile operators to validate end-to-end Radio Access Network performance by emulating real network traffic over both radio and O-RAN fronthaul interfaces.
RuSIM	RuSIM enables infrastructure vendors, chipset providers, and mobile operators to easily perform functional, conformance, and performance testing of O-RAN distributed units (O-DUs) over fronthaul functional split option 7.2x.
N6705c DC Power Analyzer	The N6705C DC Power Analyzer provides unrivalled productivity gains for sourcing and measuring DC voltage and current into the DUT.
AC6803B Basic AC Power Source	The AC6803B basic AC power source offers stable, reliable power up to 2000 VA. An intuitive user interface and flexible I/O connectivity. It can be programmed to various output characteristics and measures the consumption of the connected load.
O-RAN Studio	Open RAN Studio includes powerful O-RAN focused tools to construct, play, capture, and measure O-RAN traffic over 10 Gbps to 25 Gbps (fronthaul) Ethernet interfaces.
VXG Vector Signal Generator	VXG Vector Signal Generators are a high-end solution for millimeter wave signal generation applications.
AC Power Analyzer	The PA2203 IntegraVision Power Analyzer allows for voltage, current, and power traces to be shown for four distinct channels in real time.
Novus	Novus load modules give the flexibility and scale needed to validate from 100Mbps to 100GE technologies. They support validation of Layers 2 through 7 with Keysight's IxNetwork and IxLoad test solutions.
MTRX	The E6464A Multi Transceiver RF Test Set provides up to 64 VSA and up to 64 VSG in one instrument. Highly scalable and featuring an advanced digital MIMO and massive MIMO signal weighing matrix, it is purpose built to support beamforming measurements in these contexts.
PROPSIM	The programmable multiport time and phase coherent PROPSIM RF transceiver platform provides full control on RF signal time, phase, and amplitude. In addition to real-time RF channel emulation, PROPSIM platforms support RF signal measurements and signal waveform transmissions with embedded signal analyzer and waveform generators.
Nemo Wireless solutions	Nemo Network solutions improve the user experience and the quality of a network in a cost-effective way leveraging

	<p>optimized and automated processes. In this case, three key parts of the Nemo ecosystem will be implemented. The Nemo Handy Handheld Measurement Solution is an Android application that measures wireless diagnostics information with regard to the air interface and QoS/QoE for mobile applications. A higher understanding of the performance in these cases can be achieved with the Nemo Outdoor NR Drive Test Solution. Allowing for the measure of real user QoE and supporting all stages of the mobile network lifecycle, the collected data can be subjected to comprehensive post-processing to analyze and glean subtle insights. Further post-processing and analyses for any data gathered can be done using the Nemo Analyze Drive Test Post Processing Solution.</p>
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Table 3. Keysight Hardware tools.

3 TRIAL NETWORK'S LIFE-CYCLE AND MANAGEMENT

3.1 TRIAL NETWORK OVERVIEW

The architecture of a Trial Network (TN) was described in D2.1. This section presents how a TN can be deployed based on the requirements of the experimenter. The deployment procedure is schematically depicted in Figure 3 which shows all involved building blocks. From left to right, the procedure is as follows:

- First, the experimenter accesses the 6G-SANDBOX facility through a portal, open to experimenters and supporting different profiles and access levels.
- The experimenter will then define the Trial Network in a descriptor, which comprises the needed components and specific configurations.
- After that, the Trial Network Life-Cycle Manager (TNLCM), which is a key component developed in 6G-SANDBOX, will receive the specified TN descriptor and will ensure that all necessary information is provided for the creation of the TN. More details about TNLCM can be found below in this section.
- Finally, TNLCM initiates the deployment of the requested TN. For this purpose, the TNLCM interacts with Jenkins, which oversees the requesting deployment and manages configurations changes. Section 4 below explains in more detail how the TN resources are deployed and how they are configured.

Figure 3. Procedure for Trial Network deployment and configuration.

3.2 TRIAL NETWORK LIFECYCLE

The Lifecycle of a Trial Network refers to all the possible states in which a Trial Network can be, from its definition as a Trial Network Descriptor until its decommissioned. At any time, a Trial Network may transition to a different state (e.g., from 'Running' to 'Paused' or 'Destroyed') or its description may be updated, leading to the creation, removal, or re-configuration of components inside the Trial Network. There are no pre-conceptions regarding the amount of time a Trial Network may persist, its usage or the number of users that can perform experimentation in it.

The TNLCM (Trial Network Life-Cycle Manager) is, within the 6G-SANDBOX Architecture, the entity that ensures that every Trial Network in each platform is accessible and in working order, as well as orchestrates the necessary actions required for changing the state of a Trial Network when necessary. To do this, it makes use of both its own features as well as managing and delegating the execution of certain workflows to other components in the same layer (the Experimentation Lifecycle Layer) or the layer below (the Resource Management Layer).

3.3 TNLCM DESIGN AND ARCHITECTURE

The TNLCM has been designed as a modular application, with the intention of making certain components easily replaceable or extended, while minimizing the effect of changes in other parts of the application. At the same time, there is an emphasis on re-usability, where several data structures and generic logic can be shared between the different components of the application.

By following these ideas, the TNLCM architecture is currently organized in the following components:

- **Core:** The Core component implements the basic logic for the management of the lifecycle of the Trial Networks and the functionality required for communicating with the Resource Management Layer. It's also responsible for exposing the REST API that other components of the TNLCM, platform owners and experimenters can use for creating, managing and inspecting Trial Networks.
- **Front-End:** The Front-End included with the TNLCM is a web application tailored for use by the platform owners and, as such, will provide information and functionality for handling all the Trial Networks on the platform. To achieve this, the Front-End makes use of the APIs exposed by the Core component. Other Front-Ends, for example, a simplified one tailored for Experimenters or Trial Network owners can be developed by making use of the same APIs, either by an external developer or by the 6G-SANDBOX consortium.
- **Scheduler(s):** Schedulers can make use of the APIs exposed by Core for automatically retrieving information about the status of one or more Trial Networks, and to perform changes to the status or configuration of such Trial Networks. Multiple schedulers may be active at the same time, each accessing different Trial Networks, while also Trial Network owners may manually, or through a Front-End, use the same APIs for modifying and inspecting the status of their Trial Networks.

The components described above are active applications, that is, they are expected to be running processes in a host machine, that communicate between them, and with external entities by making use of REST APIs. In addition to these components, the TNLCM includes a separate '**Shared**' package, which contains re-usable data structures and logic, such as:

- **TrialNetworkDescriptor** and **EntityDescriptor**, which structure the data contained in a Trial Network Descriptor and provide additional methods that ease the creation of auxiliary data from the descriptor.
- **TrialNetwork** and **Entity**, which store the run-time status of a Trial Network and the entities it contains.
- **Playbook**. A Playbook is the entity that contains all the logic and work-flow definitions required for interacting (i.e., creating, destroying, modifying, etc.) with any kind of Entity that may be part of a Trial Network. This information is contained in the 6G-Library, which the TNLCM references. The Playbook class encapsulates the logic required for creating snapshots of this information (so that an update in the 6G-Library does not inadvertently break functionality on an existing Trial Network), and for providing easy access to the different workflows.
- **Library**. The Library class encapsulates the logic for interacting with the 6G-Library. It currently supports accessing multiple git repositories, each containing the definition of several types of components, and abstracts the logic required for moving between different branches and commits, and to retrieve the information corresponding to a single component.
- Several classes that provide more generic functionality, including:
 - **Log**, that handles the creation of separate log files with different severity levels, the re-direction of messages to multiple outputs, such as the terminal (with color support) and files, and the management of traces, to ease debugging in case of unhandled exceptions.
 - **Child**, that eases the creation of independent threads and provides additional functionality for handling the usage of temporary folders and the creation of logs.
 - **Cli** and **IO**, which provide access to the command line and ease the usage of the file system, respectively.
 - **ConfigBase**, which is used, via inheritance, for the creation of configuration files for all components. It includes ready-to-use logic for automatically creating files containing a default configuration and to automatically validate the correctness of the settings provided by the user.

3.4 TNLCM IMPLEMENTATION

The TNLCM is being implemented using Python 3.11. The TNLCM repository contains separate folders for each major component, which can be executed independently while having access to the common definitions shared by multiple components. This organization was chosen as it leads to an easy deployment both directly in the host machine and as containerized components orchestrated using docker-compose.

For the implementation of the required REST APIs, the Flask [2] web application framework, along with the Flask-RESTX [3] extensions have been selected. Flask-RESTX eases the creation of well documented RESTful APIs, while Flask is a proven and extensible framework for web app development with a strong community and support.

With regards to the backend and the management of other components of the architecture, the TNLCM is capable of executing certain actions on its own, for example, making direct use of the

command line or ssh interfaces. More complex actions, such as those defined for each component in the 6G-Library are delegated to Jenkins. Jenkins makes a set of pipelines available, in a generic way, for the execution of common actions and as implementations of common changes to a Trial Network. These pipelines are executed by the TNLCM when required, by feeding them with the details that are specific to each Trial Network or component. An example of these interactions in the deployment of a vxlan is shown in Figure 4.

Figure 4. Example of TNLCM-Jenkins interaction.

Every Trial Network managed by the TNLCM is in a certain state (such as ‘Running’, ‘Paused’, etc.). The Lifecycle of the Trial Network is implemented as transitions between different states. In order to encapsulate and better organize the implementation, the TNLCM defines a set of ‘Transition Handlers’, each inheriting from a base implementation but which contain the specific logic required for transitioning to a particular state. The management of the Lifecycle is done in a partially asynchronous manner:

At any given time, through the use of the TNLCM APIs, a scheduler or a user can mark a Trial Network for transition. Independently, the TNLCM periodically (currently in 5 second intervals) checks the status and information of every registered Trial Network. When required, the TNLCM generates a new Transition Handler, to perform the necessary changes for the Lifecycle of a specific Trial Network. Since Transition Handlers are implemented as independent threads, multiple ones can work in parallel on different Trial Networks.

3.5 TNLCM INTERFACES

The TNLCM API is composed of different sections, as depicted in Figure 5:

Figure 5. TNLCM API sections.

Playbook Section:

Responsible for handling and controlling the connection with 6G-Library. It consists of an endpoint:

- A GET request that is still under development.

Testbed Section:

Responsible for creating the TN. Two endpoints are available:

- A GET request that returns the IDs of the TNs that have been created and initialized.
- A POST request that creates the TN. In the POST request, a .yaml file must be attached, which is the TN descriptor containing the desired components. It will return the ID of the TN. The baseline example of a descriptor for POST request is shown in Figure 6, which can be used to create a VM with the interface indicated in the VXLAN component.

```

Infrastructure:
  VXLAN:
    Type: VxLan
    Expose: [Id]
  BASTION:
    Type: Bastion
    Connections:
      Interface: VXLAN.Id # one_component_networks: [0, Id]
    
```

Figure 6. Descriptor of POST request from Testbed Section to create a vx_lan and a bastion.

Trial Network Section:

Three endpoints are available:

- A GET request where the TN's ID must be specified, returning the entire deployment that has been carried out.
- A PUT request where the TN's ID must be specified to initialize it. It will return a message indicating that the TN has been marked for initialization.

- A DELETE request that deletes the initialized TN.

3.6 6G-LIBRARY AND COMPONENT'S DESCRIPTION

The 6G-Library is the repository in 6G-SANDBOX that describes all the components which can belong to a Trial Network. The TNLCM retrieves the instructions to deploy each Trial Network component by using the descriptions in the 6G-Library.

The description of 6G-Library objects has been included in Deliverable 3.1 Sections 2.3 and 4.1. Section 2.3 describes the structure of 6G-Library objects including the automation tools used, while Section 4.1 describes the 6G-Library repository.

4 RESOURCE AND NETWORK MANAGEMENT

4.1 RESOURCE MANAGEMENT LAYER INTERFACES

OpenNebula has been chosen as a Virtual Infrastructure provider for the components of a Trial Network.

Like most cloud providers, OpenNebula exposes a series of APIs so that the management of the cloud itself can be done using third-party tools, such as Terraform, which is the tool that we have selected in the project for the creation and management of virtual infrastructure.

Terraform has become a standard in the industry, generating a large community and multitude of documentation, as well as integration with a multitude of cloud providers, which is a great advantage if in the future any new site that wants to join the project wants to use a cloud provider other than OpenNebula.

A Trial Network is made up of several components of the 6G Library (i.e., a Bastion¹, VNETs, etc.). The TNLCM is the orchestrator in charge of deploying each of the components and managing the life cycle of the Trial Network itself.

Each of the components of the 6G Library have been designed to be defined completely through declarative files, only as code, and each of them is completely self-contained, so that it can have a life cycle, for example, be versioned, without affecting the rest of the components, the TNLCM or the trial networks that are already deployed.

When a component is included in a Trial network, there are a series of input variables and dependencies that have to be managed by the TNLCM.

When the TNLCM has all the information necessary to deploy a component, it sends the request to a Jenkins pipeline, which uses the component definition itself to deploy the necessary infrastructure through Terraform, using the component definition itself, and then configuring itself and others, if necessary, through the use of Ansible, another industry standard tool.

¹ The term "Bastion" is used to refer to a Bastion host (or jump server), which is a server on a trial network that hosts various services (e.g., DHCP, DNS, VPN, etc.) and manages external access to the Trial Network. In most use cases, Bastion implements a VPN server that enables remote access to the Trial Network.

Figure 7. Procedure and Components for TN infrastructure deployment and configuration.

Depending on the nature of each component, we will have those that deploy infrastructure and configuration, others only configuration, others only infrastructure and others only information, but the principles to define them and the tools are not always the same.

To assist in the process of deploying a Trial Network, OpenNebula is making several improvements to facilitate the process and provide as much information as possible to the TNLCM.

4.2 UPDATES TO OPENNEBULA AND TERRAFORM

To achieve the goals proposed in this project, the following improvements have been made by OpenNebula Systems:

4.2.1 DEPLOYMENT IMPROVEMENTS

one-deploy is a set of ansible playbooks that have been implemented to automate the deployment of an OpenNebula infrastructure. It allows a full deployment of a High-Availability (HA) cluster, declaring all the necessary nodes and networks.

4.2.2 POWER MEASUREMENT ON THE VMs

In order to obtain power metrics for the running VMs, scaphandre [4] has been used. This software allows getting granular power measurement the RAPL (Running Average Power Limit) extensions.

4.2.3 ONEKE IMPROVEMENTS

The service OneKE is provided by OpenNebula systems and deploys a Kubernetes cluster over an already running infrastructure. To improve the functionality and make it a better fit for the project, the following features have been implemented:

- Container Network Interfaces (CNI) added (Multus and Calico).
- Improvement of the air-gaping of Kubernetes to speed up deployments.

- Improvement of the stability and usability in the management of the cluster.

4.2.4 TERRAFORM IMPROVEMENTS AND BUGFIXES

OpenNebula's Terraform provider had a few bugs that were detected and fixed to use in this project to support the full deployment of complex applications services. This is needed to automatically deploy k8s clusters (OneKE) as part of the trial network.

The two main issues that were addressed were:

- Identification of several bugs in Terraform provider (solved with Telefonica help).
- Extend the provider to include additional data to automate the TN deployment (communicate VIP from LB services).

5 PLATFORM'S EVOLUTION AND INTEGRATION ACTIVITIES

The four 6G-SANDBOX Platforms are managed by different entities and therefore apply different rules and concepts. For the duration of the 6G-SANDBOX project, the testbeds will constantly be upgraded, and the approaches should be kept as aligned as possible to provide a seamless experience for the experimenters. To get the platforms up quickly to support the Open Call 1 as soon as possible each platform applied its own way of adding new components. Some of the platforms will loosely follow the approaches adopted during the 5Genesis project as some of the partners were part of that consortium.

Since the report in D2.1, the platforms received individual updates which will be described in the following subsection on a per-platform level. As most of the Tools that are developed for the 6G-SANDBOX project are still under development the approach is to first integrate the tool into the "Home Platform" of the developing Partner. After the component matures, it will be tested by the other platforms following the initial documentation provided in the Project in the 6G-SANDBOX GitHub group which also hosts the 6G-Library. As for now most of the tools will follow a Declarative distribution based on containers or virtual machine images. This will allow the easy deployment of the component on the target platform hypervisor with minimal configuration of the network details.

The **Berlin** Platform for instance provides an isolated section on the Shared testbed which includes multiple networks and capacity on the existing VMware cluster with access to shared RAN components. Dedicated resources are added to the project tenant reserved for the 6G-SANDBOX project in addition to the shared services. New components developed by the 6G-SANDBOX consortium will be deployed using container techniques into the existing VMware cluster. The dedicated OpenNebula cluster will be utilized for the automatic deployment of experiments using the 6G-SANDBOX tools like the common TNLCM. Custom-tailored VPN connectivity is provided for experimenters as well as platform extensions from the Open Call 1.

Athens Platform approach regarding the integration activities revolves around reserving resources on the updated cloud infrastructure to cater to the necessary software components and tools vital for the project's success. Additionally, a key aspect of this approach is establishing and providing VPN connectivity specifically for designated servers intended to host components and developments coming from the selected phase 1 open callers (OnemNEF and ANALYSAT). For hardware-based integrations, the first step involves allocating appropriate space, followed by wiring and configurations of the components. This process ensures their seamless connection to the cloud infrastructure and

the testbed overall. Following up the advancements of the project, an automated approach of deploying components through TNLCM and Jenkins pipeline will be adopted.

Malaga Platform integration strategy must be differentiated depending on whether deployed tools are hardware or software. For hardware, particularly Keysight equipment, specific locations have been reserved to allocate the equipment. The work has been focused on providing connectivity to the new rooms and initial configurations to prove interoperability with the rest of the platform. Regarding software tools, a cloud-based approach has been followed to accommodate the new services. Additionally, an initial Trial Network has been manually deployed using OpenNebula infrastructure to host the services of Open caller Arrow. Once automated mechanisms to deploy Trial Networks are finalized, this will become the standard integration approach for software tools.

Oulu Platform regarding integration targets deploying an application server to connect the upper controller and proving VPN connectivity for external parts to access the resources, configurations, or customized applications within the 5GTN platform. A major part of this approach is to deploy cloud-based applications and test services over the 5GTN platform and provide service to external requesters. Regarding cloud-based applications, a cloud-based XR service and Digital Twins Box from ICTF will be integrated via 5G modems (from OC1 RADIANT) plus 5GTN-SIM cards.

5.1 PLATFORM EXTENSIONS DEVELOPED DURING OC1

Platform extensions that were developed by third parties during the Open Call 1 will be added to all 6G-SANDBOX platforms after they are successfully integrated into the particular Pilot Platform.

The **ANALYSAT** OC1 currently under development in the Athens platform (NCSR site), aims at delivering a technical solution that evolves around three main functionalities: NWDAF, Location information, and multi-link backhaul management. Moreover, ANALYSAT has the objective of demonstrating how the three new proposed functionalities can jointly support the introduction of novel management features for network automation in satellite enabled mobile networks. This is achieved through the implementation of a use case application that exploits the information data from the new Network Data Analytics and Location Services (LCS). It is exposed by the mobile network to automatically select between satellite and terrestrial backhaul link technologies, based on aggregated mobility and traffic load analytics data, as well as on the basis of predictions built via ML techniques. However, with the aim of implementing a flexible solution, ready and easy to be deployed and integrated in other testbeds as well, ANALYSAT will deliver a self-contained approach that integrates NWDAF and the Location Management Function (LMF) capabilities within the opensource free5GC platform and will be exposed through CAPIF for other experimenters. At the time of the writing of this deliverable, the different machines hosting the nwdaf core component, and the free5GC UPF and SMF deployments have already taken place. The initial version of the Location Measurement Function into the free5GC framework is under development, as well as the ODL controller being configured on top of the 5G infrastructure.

The **ONEmNEF** solution is designed to seamlessly integrate a microservices-based Network Exposure Function (NEF) into three distinct testbeds: Athens, Malaga, and Berlin platforms. This solution offers NEF services related to QoS control, analytics, event monitoring, and traffic influence. Given the microservices-based architecture of the NEF solution, the containers (services) will be deployed within a k8s cluster. Moreover, the implementation plan includes the integration of a demo application function, which will send various requests to the NEF to validate its core services based on specific use

cases. However, ONEmNEF plans to utilize use cases from 6G-SANDBOX and/or from external experimenters whether it is feasible. The NEF will adhere to the CAPIF, ensuring that all NEF services will be accessible to experimenters in a secure and standardized manner. As of the current deliverable, the NCSR testbed aligns with the cloud-native paradigm, decomposing Open5GS into microservices. The extension aims to deploy the containerized 5GC NFs into the same K8s cluster where NEF will be deployed. Finally, the interaction of ONEmNEF's solution with the 5GS will be validated end-to-end, including the RAN, transport and core (i.e., within K8s) domains.

The **6G-LoRaGRAN** OC1 project aims to enhance the capabilities of the 6G-SANDBOX platforms by integrating LoRaWAN functionalities. This integration involves connecting LoRaWAN gateways, devices, and network/application servers at the University of Granada through standardized 3GPP protocols to the 6G-SANDBOX platform. Depending on the platform's features, this connection will be established either through the 'Non-3GPP InterWorking Function' (N3IWF) or as a simulated gNodeB/UE combination. The initial development and integration phases will take place on the Berlin platform as a pilot site. The 6G-LoRaGRAN testbed will empower researchers to conduct LoRaWAN experimental campaigns through a web interface. This interface enables them to select a 6G-SANDBOX platform, customize traffic generation patterns, and create as well as assign radio resources to LoRaWAN network slices. A REST API will be accessible to modify the assignment of radio resources to nodes based on real-time metrics, allowing the evaluation of the performance of different radio resource assignment solutions. Additionally, all LoRaWAN traffic, along with its metadata (e.g., RSSI, SNR, selected channel, and spreading factor), will be available through an MQTT interface.

The **ASTRAL** OC1 project proposes an O-RAN solution based on an open software-defined radio testbed that interacts with near-Real-Time (near-RT) RAN Intelligent Controllers (RIC). This work is currently under deployment in the Malaga platform. The testbed aims to provide realistic use cases and facilitate progress in RAN data collection for smart network resource management. The project leverages open-source libraries, such as srsRAN, and establishes a standardized E2 interface for data exchange between RAN and near-RT RIC. This integration supports the 6G-SANDBOX Consortium's goal of expanding with new open-source RAN and RIC functionalities, promoting standardized interfaces and exposing services through 3GPP CAPIF-aligned APIs. Finally, the added functionalities by ASTRAL contribute to four main domains in the 6G evolution: Slicing and Dynamic Resource Allocation, Intelligent RAN Optimization and Management, Open Interfaces for Enhanced Service Innovation, and Integration of Advanced Technologies.

The **ARROW** OC1 project aims to conduct a series of systematic experiments using an SDN-based platform that provides AI-powered digital security mechanisms as a holistic software solution with interconnected engines. In pursuit of this objective, ARROW will deploy its security framework adapted to the characteristics of the Malaga platform within 6G-SANDBOX. Following successful deployment, they will extend the capabilities of the AI-enabled SDN system offering a complete experimental environment for cybersecurity for 5G and beyond ecosystems. The proposed SDN implementation in ARROW emerges as an optimal solution, offering enhanced security and network adaptability. It serves as a complement to microservices orchestrators like Kubernetes, facilitating: (i) real-time monitoring across all network elements centrally; (ii) the implementation of threat identification modules for real-time detection of existing and unknown threats; and (iii) the establishment of real-time security events throughout the entire network based on threat identification module decisions.

The **RADIANT** OC 1 project aims to design and develop 5G Rel-16-compatible modems that will allow 6G-SANDBOX consortium members to experiment on the four different infrastructures. The main objectives of the proposed infrastructure components are: (i) to provide 5G modems that fulfil the three profiles, that is, small size modems, medium size modems and fixed CPEs; (ii) to participate in the integration and validation of the 5G modems; (iii) to provide support for field test measurements, maintenance, and potential upgrades. To this end, these modems, which represent a natural evolution of existing 5G Release-15 modems, will be developed, integrated and validated in the Oulu platform at first, then the testing, different field tests and related measurements and evaluation will be extended to the other three platforms. This also includes the support for software and hardware maintenance, as well as potential upgrades that need to be performed during the entire lifetime of the 6G-SANDBOX project.

The **RAYPLICATE** OC1 proposes to integrate its advanced ray-tracing capabilities into the Digital Twin (DT) of the Malaga platform, introducing two key components: the Volcano propagation model and the Volcano Channel package. These components provide accurate 3D-ray tracing for sub-6GHz, millimeter-wave, and sub-THz bands across various environments, supporting large-scale urban scenarios to smaller-scale simulations within buildings. The Volcano Channel package predicts radio channel properties with a graphical user interface and script mode, enabling the computation of wideband, MIMO, dynamic, and upcoming RIS-based radio channel coefficients. The proposal emphasizes the accuracy, robustness, and computational speed of the solution. Also, a collaboration with Keysight is expected for accurate PHY-layer simulations and integrations with Exata Digital Twin and the 5G/6G channel emulator on the Malaga platform. Additionally, accurate geographical map data for two specific scenarios (Malaga downtown and Ada Byron building) within the Malaga platform will be created, integrating realistic building details and base-station information.

5.2 ATHENS PLATFORM

5.2.1 OVERALL DESCRIPTION

As outlined in D2.1, the Athens platform's planned activities for infrastructure enhancement involve expanding existing functionalities and upgrading or replacing components to support the features and the framework of the 6G-SANDBOX facility. As of the writing of this document, various enhancements have been implemented in both NCSR and COSMOTE sites, as visually represented in Figure 8. The updates and added components are highlighted in red framework, while forthcoming updates are indicated in orange. The green color represents the main components of the platform that were installed previously.

Figure 8. Athens platform updated version.

5.2.2 NCSR SITE

The NCSR site has undergone several updates encompassing both hardware and software components. The enhancements made to the platform are as follows and detailed in the paragraphs that follow:

- Proxmox servers' node upgrade
- Private Container Registry
- Installation of 5G SA Ericsson gNB (BBU and RRU)
- Open5GS Integration
- Athens Digital Twin Preparation
- Installation of Keysight Tools
- OpenNebula
- NTN Setup & Configurations

5.2.2.1 PROXMOX SERVERS NODE UPGRADE

The PROXMOX node of NCSR site of Athens platform is composed of three Dell PowerEdge R350 servers, which have undergone an upgrade process in both storage and memory resources in order to increase the number of instances that can be supported concurrently, improving in this way the number of experimenters that the platform can support. The total capacity has now reached 7.5 TB SSD of storage, 1TB SSD High Availability storage, and 384 GB of RAM. Therefore, these improvements aim to support the experimental activities of the project and accommodate future use cases and requirements coming from the open callers and the experimenters.

Figure 9. Proxmox servers in Athens platform (NCSR).

5.2.2.2 PRIVATE CONTAINER REGISTRY

In NCSR cloud infrastructure hosted on Proxmox, a private docker registry to enhance the efficiency and security of the containerized applications is established. This Docker registry is encapsulated within a container image, specifically using the "registry" image [https://hub.docker.com/_/registry]. To ensure controlled access and protect the registry from unauthorized users, a Nginx reverse proxy is implemented within a VM. Nginx plays a crucial role in managing HTTP authentication for the sites it oversees, giving the capability to enforce access restrictions on the private registry. By configuring Nginx to authenticate users, an additional layer of security is added. Within the Proxmox VM, Nginx efficiently handles incoming requests and acts as a reverse proxy for the private docker registry.

5.2.2.3 INSTALLATION OF 5G NB (ERICSSON BBU AND RRU)

An upgrade in the available mobile communication offerings of the Athens platform also included the installation of the ERICSSON 5G SA at both NCSR and COSMOTE sites. More specifically, both sites were equipped with an ERICSSON Baseband Unit (BBU) 6630, which are driving via a fiber link either external ERICSSON RRUs or via the ERICSSON IRU 8848 indoor ERICSSON dot RRUs. NCSR site is equipped with two indoor ERICSSON RRU units and one outdoor ERICSSON RRU unit. For the internal ERICSSON RRU units, the installation of UTP Cat.6A cable was required and it was properly performed during the reporting period.

Figure 10. BBU and RRU units in Athens platform (NCSR site).

Finally, for powering the ERICSSON BBU and RRU units, a dedicated FLATPACK-S 2KW 48V PSU Type A unit is used to provide the units with the necessary vDC power.

Figure 11. PSU unit for BBU and RRU in Athens (NCSR site)

5.2.2.4 ATHONET 5G SA CORE

The ERICSSON BBU is enabled by the ATHONET 5G SA core deployment that is located in the COSMOTE site. The connectivity between the core and the BBU of the NCSR site is achieved via the dedicated fiber link that was described in 5.2.2.3.

5.2.2.5 OPEN5GS INTEGRATION

Following the evolution of cloud technologies, the Athens Platform has evolved to align with the cloud native paradigm. In this context, the Open5GS open-source implementation of the 5GC is decomposed into containers representing a microservices-based architecture. Each NF is a standalone container (e.g., AMF, UPF, NRF) with the necessary dependencies including protocols, signaling, SBI, etc. Adopting microservice-based 5GC architecture reveals several benefits since NFs adhere in the cloud-native paradigm. These benefits include improved automation, efficient orchestration and monitoring. Consequently, the lifecycle of 5G NFs can be automated through established frameworks like Kubernetes and they can properly exploit the cloud's built-in resilience, scaling and self-healing.

The decomposition of the services is based in a multi-stage docker build, which allows the creation of intermediate images for building a final docker image. This approach is a best practice for optimizing docker images by separating the build environment from the runtime environment. It reduces the size of the final image and limits the number of unnecessary dependencies in the runtime image. Explained differently, each NF is a docker image of approximately 300 MB size that was built from a base image of 1.15 GB that contains the entire Open5GS project, see Figure 12. Additionally, the database (i.e., MongoDB) along with the build-in web UI, used to manage subscriber-related information, are containerized. For monitoring and representing metrics, Prometheus and Grafana are utilized, respectively. It should be noted that all the docker images are stored in a private docker registry implemented in NCSR site.

amf	v2.6.6	e4c1b14d7e6e	3 weeks ago	305MB
upf	v2.6.6	47354c47dcf4	3 weeks ago	304MB
open5gs-webui	v2.6.6	dfa29baea21e	3 weeks ago	1.12GB
udr	v2.6.6	5bca29375381	3 weeks ago	306MB
smf	v2.6.6	c5dbbce8d4f5	3 weeks ago	313MB
pcf	v2.6.6	a89df6fcd24	3 weeks ago	307MB
bsf	v2.6.6	f84390632ffe	3 weeks ago	287MB
udm	v2.6.6	fa84d80b0efa	3 weeks ago	287MB
ausf	v2.6.6	cc0f4c2fa90d	3 weeks ago	287MB
nssf	v2.6.6	203599a63312	3 weeks ago	287MB
nrf	v2.6.6	53c2a5992e02	3 weeks ago	287MB
base	v2.6.6	34c0447d18ae	3 weeks ago	1.15GB
mongo-express	latest	a239c27c8e22	4 weeks ago	247MB
prom/prometheus	latest	22010d1e5539	4 weeks ago	245MB
grafana/grafana-oss	latest	00a157ed8c1f	4 weeks ago	392MB
monqo	4.4.10	275f79a10a88	24 months ago	437MB

Figure 12. Decomposition of Open5GS services.

At the time of the writing of this deliverable, the RAN solutions that have been successfully tested and connected to the containerized Open5GS include:

- Amarisoft RAN
- UERANSIM (both monolithic and containerized)
- srsRAN (srsRAN gNB with srsUE over ZeroMQ-based setup)

5.2.2.6 ATHENS DIGITAL TWIN PREPARATION

A key development within the scope of 6G-SANDBOX is the provision of the Athens platform Digital Twin using the EXata digital twin platform. Given that the availability of RAN equipment is limited i.e. only on Ericsson gNB is available, the focus on the Athens platform is to create an EXata scenario for the basic configuration of the 5G SA network available in NCSR (one gNB attached to the core) that would allow the individual execution of multiple lab-scale tests.

The currently completed activities, apart from the appropriate EXata platform installation include the establishment of a basic topology on the NCSR campus map, involving a gNB, 5G core, and UE mobility. This fundamental scenario serves as a prerequisite for advancing to more intricate topologies, facilitating meaningful comparisons between emulation results and real-world measurements, during the project's lifetime.

Figure 13. Basic configuration and topology of 5G SA AT NCSR campus.

In addition to the aforementioned, two supplementary scenarios were also examined, specifically focusing on a slicing concept and the seamless handover between two gNBs. The relevant topologies are presented in the pictures below.

Figure 14. Scenario for slicing configurations and measurements in EXata.

Figure 15. Scenario for seamless handover in EXata.

5.2.2.7 INSTALLATION OF KEYSIGHT TOOLS

Given that the project has established a standard set of testing tools that should be accessible on each platform for experimental purposes, NCSR D site has been enriched with the incorporation of a set of test and measurement software tools provided by Keysight in order to amplify the capabilities of the platform. The tools have been successfully installed into the existing infrastructure and geared towards facilitating comprehensive testing and measurements as a valuable support for the experimenters. More specifically, the tools that have been installed are as follows: CloudPeak, Cyperf, EXata and LoadCore.

5.2.2.8 OPENNEBULA

An OpenNebula instance has been installed to act as an infrastructure manager, streamlining the diverse capabilities within the NCSR D testbed, as shown in Figure 16. It facilitates the efficient management and orchestration of the heterogeneous infrastructure components and the various resources under a unified entry point, supporting both experimenters and open callers. Moreover, a DELL R630 server with two processors has been dedicated for the needs of the OpenNebula cloud computing system, which has been also upgraded in terms of memory and storage resources by partner INF for hosting the emulated NTN component, without minimizing its capability to host additional experimental components. Specifically, the memory resources have been upgraded to 96 GB RAM and the storage resources to 1.5 TB SAS HDD.

Figure 16. Main interface of OpenNebula in Athens platform (NCSR D site).

5.2.2.9 NTN SETUP AND CONFIGURATIONS

Within the scope of NTN activities, a tool to emulate satellite communication systems (OpenSAND) has been deployed. The emulator has been installed on virtual machines within the OpenNebula instance, as shown in Figure 17. The emulated satellite network comprises three entities: the satellite gateway, the satellite, and the satellite terminal. The cloud-based deployment facilitates easy scalability, allowing users to adjust computational resources based on the specific requirements of their testing scenarios.

Figure 17. Dedicated VMs for the NTN setup in OpenNebula.

The integration of OpenSAND with the OpenNebula cloud infrastructure has been tested and validated through the development of a Multi-Link Access scenario, depicted in Figure 18, in which traffic steering was achieved, between the Terrestrial path and Non-Terrestrial path, using an SDN controller.

Figure 18. Multi-Link Access scenario.

5.2.3 COSMOTE SITE

The COSMOTE site is offering to the Athens testbed enterprise-level support, through a deployment of a 5G SA network containing Ericsson gNB and Athonet Core enterprise-level systems as well as powerful data center facilities. The enhancement of the Athens platform at the COSMOTE site accomplished through 6G-SANDBOX encompasses a series of critical activities aimed at optimizing both network performance and connectivity.

A significant accomplishment is the implementation and configurations of the direct 10G interconnection with the NCSR site, replacing the previous QnQ link, in order to drive the core part of the network to the RAN located in NCSR. This upgrade enhances data transfer speeds and overall

network reliability between the two sites of the Athens platform. As an overview, both software and hardware updates activities are accomplished for 6G-SANDBOX including:

- E2E slicing configuration & experimentation.
- NTN Backhauling.
- OpenNebula & GPU Server Installation.
- Keysight Tools.

5.2.3.1 E2E SLICING CONFIGURATION & EXPERIMENTATION

COSMOTE 5G SA deployment pertains installation and configurations on Ericsson gNBs, incorporating a variety of components like Indoor/Outdoor Antennas, DOTs, IRU, and BBU systems, connected to the ATHONET 5GC. In preparation of the beyond 5G requirements and the need to offer guaranteed performance to the 6G-SANDBOX experimenters, configuration of slicing support is deemed necessary. Two different schemas have been enhanced and tested, namely:

- DNN (Data Network Name) based slicing, utilizing two UPFs to emulate edge and core 5G network Data planes, slice selected through different DNNs, as shown in Figure 19 and Figure 20.
- SST (Network Service/Slice Type) template-driven slicing: This approach provides the capability to discriminate data flows by setting different SSTs, utilizing UERANSIM [5] in lack of appropriate UE devices, for the selection of sst/sd (eMBB slices) as shown in Figure 21 and Figure 22.

Figure 19. DNN-based slicing.

- Two UPFs to emulate edge and core 5G network Data planes
- Slicing Based on DNN; each UPF has a separate DNN
- No capability to set sst/sd to UE
- Default sst/sd for each UPF/ DNN is selected by UE/ CPE
- Validated by iperf measurements and by observing DNN selection in UE.

Figure 20. COSMOTe DNN Slicing Deployments & Results.

Figure 21. SST-driven slicing.

- At PDU layer –capability to discriminate data flows by setting different SSTs.
- We can setup more than two slices (& initiate two traffic flows with the relevant characteristics): e.g. Max DL/UL Datarates 500/10Mbps, Max DL/UL 100/20Mbps, 5QCI 5, priority levels, Pre-emption Capability, Pre-emption Vulnerability etc.
- Latency, jitter and packet size are not used to define the slice/ flow attributes. → Mainly eMBB slices can be configured.
- Two slices configured in 5GSA with different sst/sd for the same DNN/ UPF (eMBB slices)
- sst:1/ sd: null, sst:2/ sd: null
- Selection of sst/sd by UERANSIM – in lack of devices
- The registered UERANSIM gNB advertises the two slices
- Two emulated UEs with two different slices
- One emulated UE with two slices
- Validated via NGAP/NAS signaling observation.

Figure 22. COSMOTe SST-driven slicing deployments & results.

5.2.3.2 NTN CONNECTIVITY

COSMOTE is supporting the NTN initiatives of 6G-SANDBOX by evaluating the satellite backhauling connectivity. A span of activities has been scheduled in this respect, evaluating GEO (HellasSat) and LEO (Starlink) solutions, first in the 5G NSA architecture and then to the 5G SA. In the first project year, the activities evolved around GEO and LEO connectivity for NSA, as presented below. Having validated the cost-effective gains of LEO practically, it has been selected as the appropriate solution to demonstrate NTN for 6G-SANDBOX.

Figure 23. Satellite backhauling with HellaSat (5G NSA). Architecture & Performance Measurements.

Figure 24. Satellite backhauling with Starlink (5G NSA): Architecture and Performance Measurements.

5.2.3.3 INSTALLATION OF OPENNEBULA AND GPU SERVER

On the basic infrastructure of COSMOTE for the purposes of 6G-SANDBOX, the following activities were implemented:

- Aligned with the 6G-SANDBOX best practices on infrastructure virtualization, an OpenNebula instance was installed to manage and coordinate the project allocated resources, supporting the 6G-SANDBOX framework. Open Nebula deployment infrastructure at COSMOTE is equipped with 28 CPUs, 283 GB RAM, and 7.2 TB of total storage across four disks. This

deployment serves as an onsite cloud provider alternative, enabling us to efficiently deploy, manage, and utilize virtual machines (VMs). While the deployment is in its nascent stage, its primary objective is to establish a comprehensive framework for managing VMs internally. Currently, we're in the early phases with no users actively utilizing the system. However, this setup holds immense potential to streamline operations, providing a flexible and scalable environment for the future.

- A GPU server has been incorporated into the current infrastructure to furnish the Athens platform with the capability to execute beyond 6G use cases such as XR/VR demos through powerful computational equipment as shown in Figure 25.

Apollo 6500 ProLiant XL675d Gen10 Plus, with the following specs:

- (2) AMD EPYC 7453 28-Core Processor
- 112 VCPUs
- 128 GB RAM
- 8 TB storage
- 4x NVIDIA A10 24GB PCIe NonCEC Accelerator

Figure 25. 6G-SANDBOX Athens GPU Server installed at COSMOTE.

5.2.3.4 KEYSIGHT TOOLS

Initially the SW based tools that are provided by Keysight have been successfully deployed in the infrastructure. The complete list of tools installed in COSMOTE are as follows: BreakingPoint, IxNetwork, IxLoad, CloudPeak, Hawkeye, Threat Simulator, LoadCore, and the EXata to support the simulation of the network.

A powerful Windows machine, equipped with an Intel Core i7 10700 CPU, 16 GB RAM, and a 3.4 TB hard disk, is dedicated for the supporting tools of the 6G-SANDBOX facility. On it, the Exata software is installed for the preparation of the digital twin of the existing 5G SA deployment (Athonet/Ericsson) in cooperation with NCSR D to simulate and emulate the behavior of our cooperative network. On the same network, the installed Hawkeye application shall be used to measure the overall network performance, address any issues for improved efficiency, and ensure network security from a cybersecurity standpoint. Additionally, given COSMOTE's involvement in various tests with beyond 5G networks, the IxLoad application will be used to test the quality of experience for end users utilizing the network.

5.2.4 COSMOTE INTERCONNECTIVITY

For the realization of the multi-domain Athens platform and the large deployment of the 5G SA Ericsson system, the upgrade from the existing GEANNT interconnection of the sites to dedicated high-speed fiber connectivity was necessary and was implemented early in the project's course.

COSMOTE, as a fixed telecommunication provider has undertaken the implementation of the dark fiber connectivity between the NCSR D premises and OTE Academy and the 6G-SANDBOX NCSR D and

COSMOTE engineers have completed the termination of the link to the 6G-SANDBOX testbeds from both sites through the installation of the appropriate active network equipment. Due to the long distance between the two sites (approximately 28 km), a pair of 10G SFP+ CWDM ZR was used. Also, a Mikrotik cloud router CRS-1G-16S+ with 10G optical interfaces was used for achieving both control and data plane connectivity between the two domains.

Figure 26. Cloud router switch in Athens platform (NCSR D site).

Finally, in NCSR D site various optical distributors have been used for reaching the COSMOTE cabinet located in the basement of NCSR D building, where the one end of the dedicated fiber link (owned by COSMOTE) is terminated (the other end is terminated in COSMOTE premises).

Figure 27. Optical distributors in Athens platform (NCSR D site).

5.3 BERLIN PLATFORM

Figure 28. Berlin Platform.

The Berlin testbed located at Fraunhofer FOKUS premises has undergone some extensions which are outlined in red in Figure 28 above and described in the following sections.

5.3.1 VIRTUALIZATION INFRASTRUCTURE

The four servers running the OpenNebula Hypervisor were reinstalled to support the latest version (6.8) of the toolkit. During the process, the cloud solution was given access to NFS shared storage that is provided by the testbed Netapp cluster. The NFS storage pool is shared with the already existing VMware ESXI hypervisors. The OpenNebula is running on four Dell blade servers with different Xeon CPU generations and with 128 and 256 GB of RAM. The cluster has 500 GB of shared NFS SSD Storage, 768 GB of RAM, and 168 CPU cores. The Shared storage can grow up to 6 TB depending on the needs.

The same storage cluster is utilized by the already existing VMware ESXi cluster. The ESXi cluster consists of six Cisco UCSB-B200-M5 servers with 32 cores and 255 GB RAM each.

Figure 29. Berlin Platform OpenNebula Cluster.

Figure 30. Berlin Platform Shared SSD storage.

Figure 31: Berlin Platform VMware cluster.

5.3.2 6G-SANDBOX PLATFORM TOOLS

Following the developments in the technical WPs, the Berlin platform is constantly updated with the tools developed within the 6G-SANDBOX project. The most recent enhancement is the new Trial Network Lifecycle Manager, which will coordinate the creation of trial networks to support experimentation on the platform. In addition to the internal tools, open-source tools like Terraform and Jenkins were deployed which will be utilized by the internal tools to manage the Platform.

5.3.3 EXPERIMENTER VPN ACCESS

Access to the Berlin Platform is provided by a dedicated VPN server which utilizes the Wireguard protocol to provide secure tunnels into the testbed network. For each Project, the VPN server provides an isolated instance which completely separates the traffic between each other. The VPN server is hosted as a Linux-based virtual machine on the VMware part of the testbed. By using Linux, the VPN is very flexible and can be adapted if an experimenter needs special settings or different VPN protocols. The VPN server is also used to integrate external testbeds or components from Open Callers into the Berlin platform infrastructure.

5.3.4 NTN CONNECTIONS

For the NTN use-cases, the Berlin platform provides LEO connectivity via the Starlink network. In addition to the non-exclusive Starlink device that was already available on the platform, an additional Starlink Terminal was acquired which will greatly improve the availability of the Satellite link during the experiments. In order to utilize Starlink connections inside the testbed, a VPN tunnel must be used to connect back into the testbed from the SpaceX HUB offloading point. Currently, the management of the VPN tunnels is shared with the general-purpose VPN access used for experimenters. However, an upgrade to an integrated version with support for the TNLCM component of the 6G-SANDBOX project is underway.

The NTN integration was tested with by using the Starlink system to connect a remote nomadic node to a 5gCore running in the Berlin Platform. The Nomadic node consisted of an edge server, a Nokia BBU together with power supply and Starlink in a mobile rack mounted in a Peli-case. Depending on the location of the mobile node UEs could handover between 5G cells which were connected directly to the 5GCore or via the NTN backhaul link.

Figure 32: Berlin Starlink NTN integration

5.3.5 KEYSIGHT TOOLS

The Project has decided on a baseline number of testing tools from Keysight that should be available on each platform for experimentation. In contrast to Malaga where most of the Hardware-based tools from Keysight are available due to a long-running partnership, the Berlin Platform is mostly limited to Software based Keysight tools except for two Keysight Measured AC Power Sources. The software tools have been successfully installed into the existing infrastructure using the VMware hypervisors. Currently, the following tools are installed on the platform: LoadCore, Hawkeye, and Nemo Handy & Analyze. The licenses of additional tools were received, and they will be installed in the beginning of 2024 starting with EXata and Cloudpeak. The installation order will be adapted on demand.

Software tools:

Tool	Status
Hawkeye	Installed
LoadCore	Installed
Nemo Handy	Partially installed
EXata	License received, to be installed
CloudPeak	License received, to be installed
Cyperf	License received, to be installed

Table 4. Keysight software tools status in Berlin platform.

5.3.6 RAN AND CORE NETWORKS

The Berlin platform provides mainly the Open5Gcore which is developed by Fraunhofer FOKUS. Commercial cores from Amarisoft and open-source cores like free5GS and Open5GS are also available. The Open5Gcore will be constantly improved as new releases will be made available in parallel to the internal developments of the software. On the RAN side of the platform, extensions in the O-RAN field are underway. More specifically, the O-RAN middleware of srsRAN, BubbleRAN, and Acceleran are currently under investigation to be included in the platform. The deployment of additional O-RU devices from Benetel is underway which will cover the n78 Frequency band. The installation will be

mostly indoor and will be available in addition to the already existing Nokia and Huawei infrastructure described in D2.1.

5.4 MALAGA PLATFORM

Malaga platform's infrastructure is allocated in a set of different geographic areas that are all interconnected, making up the Victoria Network. The main infrastructure was explained earlier in D2.1, but it has been extended since the beginning of the project with new functionalities that are highlighted in red in Figure 33. In the following sections these updates are explained in more detail.

Figure 33. Malaga Platform.

5.4.1 RAN

The previous O-RAN deployment in University Campus has been replaced by a new solution composed by:

- O-RU: Benetel RAN550 working in band n78. A picture of the integration is shown in Figure 34.
- O-DU, O-CU and RIC: Full solution provided by IS-Wireless.

The solution has been tested E2E with COTS UEs and completely operational for experimenters. In addition, enhancements to the current solution are under development and will be reported in WP3.

Figure 34. Benetel RAN550 RU.

This deployment coexists with previously available RAN solutions based on Nokia cells, that were explained earlier in D2.1 and remain available.

In addition, new Benetel radio RAN650 has been acquired and will extend the outdoor coverage area on the University Campus using band n77. This integration is not completed yet, as it is in the process of acquiring approval to radiate in this new frequency band. In the meantime, some initial tests with the units have been performed using Keysight tools available in Malaga. After that, the radio has been installed in the rooftop of Ada Byron building, as depicted in Figure 35, and is ready for integration when approval is acquired.

Figure 35. Benetel RAN650 RU.

5.4.2 NTN

The initial idea was to use OneWeb as the NTN provider. However, due to licensing issues to operate in Spain, this approach has been delayed and is expected to be solved during 2024.

Nevertheless, a Starlink solution has been installed in the rooftop of the Ada Byron building, and is now operative, as shown in Figure 36. The solution has been integrated with the rest of the platform and is also connected with Telefonica facilities in Peñuelas (Madrid).

Figure 36. Starlink terminal in Ada Byron building.

5.4.3 KEYSIGHT TOOLS

An important set of Keysight tools, mainly software, is expected to be deployed in all 6G-SANDBOX platforms. In addition, in the case of Malaga, also numerous hardware tools will be made available. Below can be found the status of software and hardware tools that have already been received:

Software tools:

Tool	Status
Hawkeye	Installed
LoadCore	Installed
Nemo Handy	Partially installed
Nemo Outdoor	Installed
Nemo Analyze	Installed
EXata	Installed
CloudPeak	Installed
Cyperf	Installed
PathWave Test Automation	Installed
RIC Test	Installed
BreakingPoint	License received, to be installed
IxNetwork	License received, to be installed
IXLoad	License received, to be installed
Threat Simulator	License received, to be installed

Table 5. Keysight software tools status in Malaga platform.

Hardware tools:

The following hardware tools have already been received at Malaga platform and are operative or under initial configurations.

Tool	Status
COTS Servers	Operative
Laptop and x6 UE devices for Nemo solutions	Operative
Novus	To be configured
UeSIM	Partially configured
DuSIM	Operative
CuSIM	Operative
RuSIM	Operative
N6705c DC Power Analyzer	Operative
O-RAN Studio	Operative
AC Power Analyzer	Operative
MTRX	Operative
PROPSIM	Operative

Table 6. Keysight hardware tools status in Malaga platform.

5.4.4 UE POOL

As part of the Malaga infrastructure, a new UE pool has been prepared, which consists of a set of UEs connected to a mini-PC acting as a hub. These UEs are available for experimenters and will be integrated in the Trial Networks as components that can be reserved.

5.4.5 DATACENTERS UPGRADE

Malaga platform includes two differentiated datacenters, UMA and Telefonica (Edge), which has been upgraded to allocate the forthcoming services.

On the UMA side, two new P4 [6] switches have been deployed, as depicted in Figure 37. These are programmable switches intended for the addition of telemetry capabilities to the network and the use in deterministic communications. In addition, a new COTS server has been prepared to allocate an OpenNebula solution and other services on demand. New servers are also expected in the future.

Figure 37. P4 Switches at UMA datacenter.

On the Telefonica side, new servers and switches have been added to the existing infrastructure and an OpenNebula instance has been installed to manage and orchestrate all resources. Over this infrastructure, different tools have been installed to manage TN creation and management (Jenkins, Terraform, Ansible...). An overview of the infrastructure is shown in Figure 38.

Figure 38. Telefonica datacenter infrastructure.

5.4.6 DIGITAL TWINS

Within 6G-SANDBOX, the commercially released EXata Network Modeling is used as the foundation for Digital Twins development. It will be enhanced using a series of 6G testbeds that will generate measurements that will calibrate the Digital Twins with real world data.

5.4.6.1 INTEGRATION OF EXATA SCENARIOS

Throughout the course of this year, Task 4.3 achieved significant milestones in advancing the 6G-SANDBOX network simulation and preparing its measurement capabilities. This deployment has laid the groundwork for enhanced simulation capabilities, providing a robust foundation for further research and development initiatives.

A major focus this year was the creation of basic EXata scenario prototypes tailored to UMA's 5G laboratories. Collaborating closely with Keysight and UMA, we developed these prototypes to closely emulate the physical setup of these laboratories. Subsequently, UMA contributed by refining and incorporating base station configurations into the scenarios, ensuring a high level of accuracy and realism in our simulations. Specifically, UMA provided 2D plans with accurate cell sites' locations and other elements relevant in the DT construction. In addition, configuration files from Nokia-based deployments were provided, including all necessary parameters to replicate operational configuration into the DT. The mapping between these configuration files and EXata requested information is not a straightforward action. Thus, this is a manual process that UMA is conducting.

In line with the commitment to create a DT based on measurements from an actual O-RU, an O-RU measurement testbed was successfully put in place as a collaboration between Keysight and UMA. This testbed will act as the foundation to create the first proof-of-concept of maximizing the accuracy of the DT by relying on actual measurement of the digitized target.

This proof-of-concept is a measurement framework to characterize the energy consumption of an O-RU DT. The energy consumption is selected as it is a concrete KPI that can be validated against real measurements to verify its accuracy. This framework will then become the template to create similar frameworks for other network nodes such as UEs and O-DUs but also other KPIs such as radio performance, coverage, etc. This key initiative is led by Keysight.

Another key aspect of this research for DT is to create an accurate model for the channel simulation. To cover this aspect, 6G-SANDBOX includes a collaboration with Siradel. The 3D ray tracer of Siradel will be integrated in the EXata digital twin platform. Thus, enhancing the EXata's accuracy for the physical layer simulations of the Malaga Digital twin platform for both 5G/6G networks. Within this collaboration we will also integrate the ray tracer of Siradel into the PropSim channel emulator. To this end, accurate geographical maps are essential. Geographical data will be created for two scenarios and will be implemented in 6G-SANDBOX platform of Malaga as follows:

- City center: the created map will be compatible with FR2 outdoor small cell predictions with submeter precision as shown in the figure below.

Figure 39. Example of Malaga city center 3D map.

- **Ada Byron Building:** The measurements will be for the Ada Byron building in University of Malaga campus and its surrounding area, that is covered by 6G-SANDBOX base-stations. A detailed 3D representation of the building will be created with accurate description for a few rooms which will be considered indoor and outdoor-to-indoor predictions.

Figure 40. Example of Ada Byron building 3D map.

For both scenarios, full detailed description (locations, antenna types, height, etc.) of the base stations will be considered. In addition, the simulation of FR2 RIS surfaces will be considered and deployed in the city center scenario. These scenario maps serve as a valuable tool for understanding signal propagation and coverage, contributing to the ongoing optimization of network performance.

5.4.6.2 CALIBRATION OF DIGITAL TWIN FOR PREDICTING ENERGY CONSUMPTION IN O-RU

By definition, a measurement-calibrated DT requires a testbed to generate the required measurements. The goal of the testbed is to emulate the parameters that the DT will receive and then measure the behavior of the digitalized Device Under Test (DUT). The testbed used to measure the O-RU DL energy is an example of how to design such a testbed. In the case of the O-RU, the testbed needs to be able to measure the energy of the O-RU and emulate the traffic that the O-DU would send to the O-RU so that it can recreate the different scenario parameters where the O-RU power consumption would fluctuate. To achieve the latter, the testbed is composed of

the O-RU as the DUT. It is connected to two instruments: A power supply (N6781A) that can provide 20V and up to 1A while maintaining high-precision measurements [7] and an S5040A, which is an O-DU emulator able to recreate an actual O-DU message for the O-RU [8]. The procedure is to trigger the S5040A to generate a message with the specified network parameters, such as MCS or bandwidth, and for the O-RU to enter an extended transmission state. Then, the N6781A can measure the power consumption. An RF detector is used to identify which part of the power consumption belongs to the TX state of the O-RU. Figure 41 and Figure 42 show diagrams of such a testbed and an actual image with the hardware assembled, respectively.

Figure 41. Diagram of the testbed to gather the measurement for the O-RU Energy DT.

Figure 42. Keysight 6G Testbed.

The DT for the energy consumption will be only the first of many DT for the 6G networks and will serve as a proof of concept. Once validated, similar testbeds will be developed for each component of the network. This list includes an O-RU but for the radio performance, UEs, O-DUs, O-CUs, etc.

5.5 OULU PLATFORM

Figure 43. Oulu Platform.

Oulu platform's infrastructure is allocated in a campus-wide area with different interconnected cells and distributed antennas to service several projects. The main infrastructure is explained in D2.1, but there have been ongoing extensions since the beginning of the project with new functionalities that are highlighted in orange in Figure 43. In the following sections, all these updates are explained in more detail.

5.5.1 INTEGRATION SERVER

To support the integration with external parts from other 6G-SANDBOX partners, Oulu provides a physical server. The server is connected to the 5GTN platform via a physical connection. It will undertake the responsibilities, including establishing connections with external parts, deploying container environments to support cloud-based applications, and deploying Keysight applications and tools to monitor performance. The server can be accessed by external users or controllers through established VPN connectivity. To support cases of customized applications over 5G, an initial operation of container-supported deployment of the DTB cloud service to support the XR service developed by ICTF. In addition, to support network monitoring and simulation, a set of Keysight tools is expected to be deployed. The physical server for integration has been received, is being configured now, and is expected to be prepared in early 2024.

5.5.2 APPLICATION HARDWARE INTEGRATION AND VPN CONNECTIVITY

Applications over the 5G/6G network are expected to be deployed over 5GTN. To support such kinds of applications, network hardware that supports relevant equipment access to the 5GTN platform will be available. We have applied for 5GTN SIM cards from Oulu. These SIM cards will be combined with the 5G modems provided by OC1 RADIANT. It is expected to provide an easy-configured connection to 5GTN for future applications. Because the 5GTN platform is protected by a firewall, to support

interconnection with external parts and enable them to access components within 5GTN, a VPN tunnel connection must be used to connect back into the 5GTN platform from the physical integration server. 5GTN is planning to switch to a new firewall in the near future, and the VPN connectivity will be deployed afterward.

5.5.3 DTB APPLICATION INTEGRATION

The DTB application for supporting XR-related applications is developed by ICTF and is part of 6G-SANDBOX. To support and integrate with it, DTB hardware will be integrated and connected to 5GTN by installing 5G modems from OC1 RADIANT plus the 5GTN SIM cards from Oulu. In addition, to support the cloud service of DTB applications, a container support environment is being deployed at the initial stage for the running of DTB microservices. The architecture of integrating DTB to 6G-SANDBOX is displayed below.

Figure 44. DTB application integration.

5.5.4 KEYSIGHT TOOLS

Conducting experiments on the platform by using testing tools from Keysight is a major expectation of 6G-SANDBOX. Considering the limitations and targets on the Oulu site, only some Keysight software tools will be installed, including OpenTAP, Hawkeye, Cyperf, Exata, and Threat Simulator. Currently, Oulu has only received licenses for these software tools. The installation, configuration, and utilization will be started after receiving the corresponding license and after the initial configuration of the integration server.

6 CONCLUSIONS AND FUTURE PLANS

The first 9-months of activities in work package 4 has produced a first version of the TNLCM and improved the features in all four 6G-SANDBOX platforms compared with their initial state. The current TNLCM is able to support proof of concepts towards getting feedback from experimenters. The platforms have new technologies coming from different sources: new components developed in WP3 in the project, hardware and software from the market and from specific MoUs with third parties and contributions from Open Call 1.

Future plans towards the final versions of the Trial network management, digital twins and integration of features in the platform are summarized below.

6.1 TRIAL NETWORK MANAGEMENT AND DEPLOYMENT

The extension of the Trial Network Lifecycle Manager (TNLCM) is a crucial step in enhancing its capabilities to support the deployment of new components from Work Package 3 (WP3) activities, Open Calls and other external sources. This extension involves a comprehensive update to the definition of descriptors, which of course involves the improvement of the 6G-Library with all these new components, ensuring that the TNLCM is well-equipped to handle the new integrations. One of the key advancements in this extension will be the establishment of a bidirectional communication channel between Jenkins and TNLCM. This will facilitate the timely and accurate dissemination of information regarding the status of deployed components. Experimenters will then easily monitor whether components are running, in use, stopped, or undergoing any other state changes, empowering them with real-time insights into the operational status of their experiments.

To achieve that, the integration of TNLCM with scheduling mechanisms will be needed, adding an extra layer of sophistication to the management of resources within the testbed environment. By incorporating scheduling capabilities, TNLCM will gain the ability to control the availability of resources dynamically. This will ensure optimal resource allocation, preventing potential conflicts and bottlenecks while maximizing the efficiency of the testbed. Thus, experimenters will be able to rely on TNLCM not only for component deployment but also for intelligent resource management, avoiding conflicts with other experimenters using same resources.

In addition, the deployment of a user-friendly front-end for TNLCM is necessary to enhance user experience. This graphical user interface (GUI) will serve as a valuable tool for experimenters, allowing them to define and configure Trial Networks (TNs) effortlessly. The intuitive interface should be able to abstract experimenters from the intricacies of specific components required for deploying a particular use case. This abstraction will simplify the process of TN definition, making it accessible to a broader audience and lowering the barrier to entry for those less familiar with the underlying technical details.

6.2 DIGITAL TWINS

The plan can be delineated into four phases, each contributing to the overall development and success of the digital twin for 6G networks. The four phases are summarized as follows:

Phase 1 – Validate the accuracy and reliability of the digital twin: In the initial stage, our primary objective is to validate the accuracy of the digital twin. Thorough testing and comparison against the radio physical channel measurements that will be conducted by Siradel which will ensure the alignment between the virtual and real-world counterparts. Any discrepancies discovered will undergo thorough analysis and adjustment, aiming for a validated digital twin that accurately represents the 5G/6G networks.

Phase 2 – Characterize the energy consumption of any part of the 5G/6G network (RU, CU, DU, UE, etc.) towards the full network of 6G: Upon successful validation of the digital twin, the project will transit to the characterization of the energy consumption of the 5G/6G networks. To this end, extensive energy measurements will be conducted using the O-RU of Benetel. The AI model will be

characterized for the energy consumption that will be based on different parameters such as the frequency, the bandwidth, antenna type, and other relevant parameters. The same concept will be followed for the different parts of the 5G/6G networks and AI energy consumption models will be extracted. Insights gained from this phase will not only enhance our understanding of the system's behavior but also inform future refinements to both the digital twin and the physical infrastructure.

Phase 3 – Apply energy efficiency techniques (Sleep mode techniques, cell on/off, channel switching, MIMO muting, etc.) to decrease the energy consumption: the third phase is focused on the implementation of energy efficiency techniques. This phase involves the deployment of intelligent algorithms and advanced techniques such as cell on/off switching, RF switching, bandwidth adaptation, cell zooming and many others. The goal is to optimize the energy consumption improving the overall efficiency and sustainability of the future networks.

Phase 4 – Understand the impact of the energy efficiency techniques on the performance of 5G/6G networks (cost in terms of coverage, data rate, throughput, QoS, etc.): this phase is centered around a comprehensive analysis of how the various energy efficiency techniques will influence the performance of the 5G/6G networks. This involves systematic experimentation to evaluate the effect of these techniques.

Throughout these phases, several approaches will be maintained involving interdisciplinary teams to ensure a holistic perspective. This approach aims to deliver a reliable and robust digital twin aligned with the energy efficiency goals while providing valuable insights into parameters influences on performance.

6.3 INTEGRATION IN ATHENS PLATFORM

- **Open5GS –K8s deployment and integration:** Following up on the work described in section 2.5.5.2, addressing the encapsulation of each NF within a standalone container, further deployment and integration activities will be performed to test the containerized functions of the 5GC within a K8s environment.
- **Extension with OC technologies:** As of the time of the writing of this document the developments coming from OC1, namely ANALYSAT, ONEmNEF, are progressing with a detailed time plan towards their finalization, thus they will be also deployed in Athens platform. Moreover, new technologies are expected to be integrated in the platform coming from OC2 phase which has been kicked off already.
- **Integration of new RAN equipment,** supporting the deployment of mmWave RAN equipment, is part of the future activities, to enable Athens platform to support experimentation with RIS.
- **Extend the 5G NTN backhaul capabilities** to the 5G SA deployment (Ericsson/Athonet).

6.4 INTEGRATION IN BERLIN PLATFORM

- **Cloud native extensions:** 5Gcores like the Open5GCore and the open-source cores need to be prepared for cloud native operation with k8s. This allows the integration with Experiments that make use of rapid deployment of components inside the Platforms k8s cluster. The

existing cloud native packages for Open5GCore will be optimized to use less resources and seamless configuration using helm charts.

- **Extension with OC technologies:** Currently the OC1 phase is in the final phase where the Open Callers finalize their contribution and bring it into the Platforms. The Extensions should already be developed and deployed in the assigned Prototype Platform and will be deployed in the following month in the other Platforms. In particular, the LoraGRAN extension is currently integrated into the Berlin Platform and the work with ONEmNEF has already started. Technologies from the Remaining OC1 participants will follow shortly. Moreover, new technologies are expected to be integrated in the platform coming from OC2 phase which has been kicked off already.
- **Integration of RAN extensions:** In addition to the already available RAN components, new equipment from Benetel and BubbleRAN is added to the platform. As a first step these components are added by manual configuration. The configuration of these components is planned to be automated so that the experiment manager could reconfigure the RAN parts on demand.

6.5 INTEGRATION IN MALAGA PLATFORM

- **Integration of new RAN deployments:** Beyond the integration of the Benetel RAN650, which is set to enhance outdoor coverage in the Ada Byron building and extend 5G solutions throughout the University campus, there are anticipations for additional RAN deployments. Specifically, the primary focus of these new advancements will revolve around expanding coverage in the Malaga city center through the implementation of mmWave solutions. Additionally, there are plans for initiating 5G deployments in entirely new locations, such as La Mayora and Malaga TechPark.
- **Integration of P4 switches:** Even though P4 switches have been already installed, it is necessary to integrate them into the network to enhance its capabilities for Telemetry purposes. P4, or Programming Protocol-Independent Packet Processors, offers advanced network programmability, allowing for precise customization of packet processing logic. By incorporating P4 switches, the network will gain real-time insights into performance, traffic patterns, and resource utilization.
- **Extension with OC technologies:** Technologies not yet deployed in Malaga coming from OC1, namely ANALYSAT, ONEmNEF, 6G-LoRaGRAN and Radiant will be also deployed in Malaga. Also, new infrastructure is expected to be integrated coming from new OC2 phase.
- **Integration of ITRI technologies.** 6G-SANDBOX has started a collaboration with Industrial Technology Research Institute (ITRI) from Taiwan. From this collaboration, new technologies will be integrated into the Malaga platform coming to support different use cases such as JCAS and RIS controlling.

6.6 INTEGRATION IN OULU PLATFORM

- **Integration of Server:** The server for integration has been deployed. However, it is necessary to deploy more software tools that come from Keysight and others for performance monitoring. Moreover, a VPN connection needs to be established for remote access and integration with external parts. In addition, to support the XR application DTB and other

applications, a container-support environment is going to be deployed for the easy deployment of applications.

- **Extension with OC technologies:** The technologies have not yet been deployed in Oulu, namely Radiant. The 5G modem from OC1 has just been received and is in the primary test phase. It will be deployed to support applications over 5GTN. Moreover, new technologies are expected to be integrated into the platform coming from the OC2 phase.
- **Integration with DTB application:** ICTF is developing XR-related applications, namely DTB. However, it has not been deployed in Oulu. After the test of 5G modems, the initial phase of deploying the DTB application will start to test the supportiveness of 5GTN for XR applications.

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